

'FAMILY' RELATED VOCABULARIES IN "WAR AND PEACE" AND "THE MAN OF PROPERTY"

VOCABULARIOS 'FAMILIARES' EN "GUERRA Y PAZ" Y "EL HOMBRE DE LA PROPIEDAD"

RESUMEN

El objetivo de la investigación fue la comparación lingüística y el análisis de vocabularios relacionados con la palabra "familia" en los libros de "Guerra y paz" de Leo Tolstoy, y "El hombre de la propiedad" de John Galsworthy. El método de recolección de datos fue documental, y el análisis de los datos se realizó mediante el método de análisis de contenido. Los resultados indicaron que Galsworthy muestra la noción de "familia" como una unidad poderosa de la sociedad o sociedad "en miniatura" con sus tradiciones sostenibles, mientras que la vieja generación intenta controlar a los miembros de la familia para ser leales a la familia. Pero en el libro de Tolstoy no hay imágenes de una familia en particular.

Palabras clave: familia, verbalización, dispositivos estilísticos, mejora de la emotividad, peyorativa de la emotividad.

ABSTRACT

The aim of research was the linguistic comparison and analysis of vocabularies related to the word "family" in two books of "War and Peace" by Leo Tolstoy, and John Galsworthy's "The Man of Property". Method of data collection was documental one, and data analysis was done by content analysis method. The results indicated that Galsworthy shows the notion of "family" as a powerful unit of society or "miniature" society with its sustainable traditions, while the old generation tries to control family members in order to be loyal to the family. But in Tolstoy's book there are no images of a particular family.

Keywords: family, verbalization, stylistic devices, ameliorative emotiveness, pejorative emotiveness.

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INTRODUCTION

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights defines family as "the natural and fundamental group unit of society" (Universal Declaration of Human Rights).

There are several definitions of the term family suggested by scholars working in the field of sociology in Russia; most of them reflect the essence of traditional family. For example, Kharchev's definition underscores that family is characterized by historically settled system of relationships between spouses, parents and children (Kharchev, 1979).

Intercultural communication studies based on the opinions of such scholars as Freeman, Showel (2010), Kohn (1963) Sharmanjiev (2016), and Murdock (1949) etc. recognizes the family as one of the three agents of socialization process (Freema & Showel, 2010; Kohn, 1963; Sharmanjiev, 2016; Murdock, 1949).

Researches in comparative studies of the English and Russian languages emphasize the existence of differences between them related to the cultures. Davletbaeva Ivanova and Kozlova write about English and Russian "phraseological units possessing cultural component" of meaning among others (Davletbaeva, Ivanova, and Kozlova, 2015). Similar conclusion is made by Gataullina, Salieva, and Aslanova on the basis of Analyzeing English and Russian phraseological units with the component denoting family relations (GataullinaVeronika, SalievaRimma, AslanovaUlduz, 2017; Kulkova, Rakhimova, and Zinecker, 2015). They write about cultural component of linguistic units on the level of German and Russian paroemiology.

Current paper analyzes means of verbalizing the social and cultural notion 'family' in the works "The man of property" by John Galsworthy and "War and peace" by Leo Tolstoy. Galsworthy's work describes the life of the Forsytes' family beginning approximately from the middle of the 19th century. Tolstoy's novel gives account of events related to the war between France and Russia starting in 1812. "The man of property", as the whole trilogy "The Forsyte Saga", is about one well-off noble British family, while as "War and peace" is about the aforementioned war and its impact on the lives of several well-off noble Russian families. Therefore, we find that comparative Analyze of picturing the family as a unit of society in these works can provide useful information related to this facet of British and Russian cultures.

Though family relations are central to both the novels, there are not so many scholarly works devoted to analyzing them from this viewpoint, (Yevdokimova, 2002). states, in her dissertation, negative or positive views of Tolstoy connected with Christianity are revealed when describing family relations. Contemporary philologists (Shilnikova) underscore dominance of the value of property over the value of family relations in this work by John Galsworthy (Shilnikova, 2016).

Moreover, modern literature studies admit the importance of comparative analysis of fiction works of different languages, V.R. Amineva calls this process "inter-literature dialogues" (Amineva, 2015).

The present paper titled "Family' Related Vocabularies in "War and Peace" and "The Man of Property", linguistically compares and analyzes vocabularies related to the word "family" in two books of "War and Peace" by Leo Tolstoy, and John Galsworthy's "The Man of Property".

METHODOLOGY

In this research, content analysis method was used to collect data. First, all family-related discourses were identified in the texts. Then the exact meaning that the term "family" implied in the texts was analyzed. Afterwards phonological and linguistic features of these texts were extracted and finally, texts that provided a description of family and family environment were identified. Following that for the concepts which were obtained, codes were allocated, and then the codes obtained from the two books were compared to determine their degree of consistency differentiation.

DISCUSSION

1. The notion "family" verbalized by Galsworthy using method of componential analysis

Family bonds are called by John Galsworthy a "tribal instinct" that was even in Victorian era "the prime force", and that "family and the sense of home and property counted as they do to this day". These words sound as a firm conviction of the writer that the family had always been of great importance in the British society.

The Forsytes, as they think, are really a very important unit of England and London, as they are a big, powerful and well-off family. Moreover, they are united by the idea of being a force as a family, which is very clearly seen from the description of two vital events when the Forsytes come together. The first one is Old Jolyon's granddaughter June and Mr. Philip Bosinney's engagement. As the fiancé was a person with no appropriate income that was something bizarre for this family with specific "sense of property" they all gathered in Old Jolyon's house. The Forsytes' opinion about this personage is expressed by the following metaphor: "strange and unsafe thing". The second time the Forsytes were brought together by the grief of losing Aunt Ann, the eldest of the Forsyte sisters.

In general, the feature of the Forsytes' family being united is depicted by the author as their positive characteristics, which is achieved with the help of various stylistic devices. Though he uses the metaphor "tribal instinct" speaking about the characteristics of the family mentioned above, Galsworthy combines this trope with the word combinations "sense of home", "sense of property" and personification "in the bravery of light gloves, buff waistcoats, feathers and frocks", metaphor "put a

burnish on their armour”, where the tropes describe expensive and beautiful clothes of the family members matching their status, Bosinney being absolutely indifferent to his outfit. It is the same function of expressing ameliorative emotiveness towards the family as a united entity, that the metaphors “the very hall-mark and guarantee of the family fortunes” denoting 5 Forsyte brothers, “had a stake in the family soul” (about each member of the family).

The older generation of the Forsytes are portrayed as trustworthy and solid people. For example, the author calls old Jolyon “the head of the family”, “the figurehead of his family”. These metaphors alongside with the epithet “white” (with his white head) and simile “dome-like forehead” used when describing this personage add to the same trait of his character. The epithets in the word combinations “inflexible back, and the dignity of her calm face”, the metaphor “backwater of the family energy” depicting another representative of this generation – Aunt Hester and the epithets “straight-backed”, “strong” about Aunt Ann should also be mentioned here. “The spirit” of Aunt Ann even when she was “lying in her last sleep had called the family to demonstrate their “tenacious unity” and “that law of property underlying the growth of their tree, by which it had thriven and spread, trunk and branches, the sap flowing through all, the full growth”. In this example one can observe the use very bright stylistic devices: the epithet “tenacious” and extended metaphor comparing the Forsytes’ family with a powerful tree in full growth.

J. Galsworthy underscores the fact of this generation of the Forsytes being very mindful and caring for the younger generation. This is evidenced by such tropes as the simile “the family she had watched like a mother”, metaphors “the spirit of the old woman ...had called”, “saw only her (Aunt Ann) own flesh and blood” (looking at her family).

The older generation of the Forsytes looked at the younger ones as their property, which is expressed by excessive use of possessive pronouns. So, for Aunt Ann “it was her world, this family” everything taking place in this family “was her property, her delight, her life”; old Jolyon calls the Forsytes “my people”. Moreover, they took even Mr. Bosinney, the person who just is engaged to old Jolyon’s granddaughter, “as belonging to the family”.

Being a noble family the Forsytes scrupulously preserve the family traditions. The following three short sentences seem to be very simple from linguistic viewpoint: “Family dinners of the Forsytes observe certain traditions. There are, for instance, no hors d’oeuvre. The reason for this is unknown”. But we see symbolic meaning in these sentences; it is about the family having their own traditions and remaining faithful to them by all means, though sometimes being not conscious of the origin of the tradition.

One more feature of this family is its tenacity. This noun and its derivatives “tenacious”, “tenaciously” are used 16 times in this book, each time in combination

with the word's "family", "the Forsytes" or the name of the most typical representatives of the family, e.g.: Soames, old Jolyon.

The Forsytes are portrayed as a family with a peculiar "sense of property", here one should mention an extremely bright metaphor "Forsytes ...have shells", followed by the hyperbole "they are never seen, or if seen would not be recognized, without habitats, composed of circumstance, property, acquaintances, and wives". Everything mentioned in this example are viewed by a Forsyte as property. It is symbolic the word "property" is part of the title and it is used 79 times in the text under analysis.

The language used by J. Galsworthy depicting such a trait of the Forsytes as their passion to discuss various rumors about other members of the family is really admirable due to the bright metaphors, e.g.: "the mist of family gossip", "family secrets were bartered", "the family tongues buzzing in his ears", etc.

2. Verbalization of the notion "family" by Leo Tolstoy using method of componential analysis

Leo Tolstoy's work describes the life of several noble families representing mostly the upper class of the Russian society, which can be seen from concise dwelling of the author on the backgrounds of these families. The writer provides this information about the Bolkonskiis when depicting their family portrait, where he uses the epithet "владетельный" denoting "possessing inherited power". This word is used when characterizing one of the ancestors of the Bolkonskiis. Tolstoy combines this trope with an allusion "Рюрик" (Ryurik) – a well-known historic figure in Russia, from whom many prince families originated. One more epithet "известный" (well-known) is utilized in combination with the name "prince Bolkonskii" and mentioning that he had a nick name "Prussian king". Though originating from such a noble family, the old prince Bolkonskii has a disgusting character that is very clearly seen from his attitude to his daughter Maria, whom he treats unfairly.

One more personage, representing the older generation of upper-class families is introduced with the help of a bright epithet знаменитый (prominent). He is Graph Cirill Vladimirovich Bezukhii who possesses even higher title – "вельможа" and his reputation is very contradictory, as he has so many illegitimate children, which is expressed by the hyperbole "Детям своим не считал" (Does not remember the number of his children).

Graph Rostov is portrayed as an affectionate father, caring head of his family and merciful person.

We can observe mostly ameliorative emotive attitude towards the family as a cultural and social notion being expressed in the work "War and peace" by Leo Tolstoy. This is achieved, firstly, by combining the word "семья" (family) with such

words as “любовь” (love), “забота” (care), “счастье” (happiness). Secondly, the author provides description of such scenes of family life where really affectionate attitude of family members to each other is demonstrated. Such scenes witness also about the unity of the family, for example, when the Rostovs were giving a ball, the head of the family and his wife were sitting at the opposite ends of the table, their children being in the middle. We find this order of arranging the family has a symbolic meaning. One more example is about the graph kissing his wife under the music beginning to play.

Here one should give the example of very frequent use of diminutive suffix with the names and other words in this function, e.g.: “графинюшка”, “матушка”, “доченька”, etc.

What concerns the relationship between the older and younger generations, it is also different in various families. The Rostov parents and children communicate with real sincerity playing, joking with each other. The father uses such a metaphor, speaking about his beloved daughter Natasha, as “попox” (gunpowder) and the epithet “славные” (glorious) about his children. We come across one more metaphor “заливаться смехом” (break into laughter) the author uses describing Natasha’s laugh at her father’s dancing during her birthday party. Though it is a dead metaphor it sounds quite interesting.

Throughout the book a reader feels the parents’ love for their children and caring about them in this family. At least one trope picturing it should be mentioned here: it is about symbolic disappearance of sun beams as it seemed to the mother when her children left the room.

Being in the family children do not pay much attention to the warmth, love they get from their parents, appearing far from home, in a difficult situation they recall this entire atmosphere. It is very vividly expressed in the description of the scene, when Nikolay Rostov is lying wounded after the battle, where the words “дом” (home) and “семья” (family) are given in combination with the words “тепло” (warm), “светло” (light), “забота” (care), “любовь” (love).

Unfortunately, the relationship between old Prince Bolkonskii and his daughter are quite different, where the father is very rude to Duchess Maria. Writing about the thoughts of this personage about his daughter Tolstoy uses such epithets as “неуклюжа” (awkward) and “дурна” (ugly). He is not grateful to his daughter even for sacrificing her private life for his sake – refusing to marry and remaining with him.

These noble families are fond of gossiping about each other which is expressed by the hyperbole used by one of the personages “в Москвe больше делать нечего, как сплетничать” (literally: there is nothing to do in Moscow than gossiping).

RESULTS

Through statistic method of concepts codification, it was found out that verbalizing the notion “family” J. Galsworthy uses the word “family” 109 times. In 44 cases the word realizes ameliorative emotional attitude to this notion; in 21 cases – pejorative emotional attitude and in 44 cases – neutral one.

In “War and peace” by Leo Tolstoy a reader comes across the word “семья” (family) only 15 times. In 7 sentences it expresses positive attitude towards this unity, in 4 sentences – neutral and in 4 sentences negative one.

Mostly the aforementioned word is used in combination with various stylistic devices among which one can find epithets, similes, hyperboles, personifications and reiteration of some words. One of the most frequent tropes in both the works under analysis is metaphor, including dead and extended ones.

CONCLUSIONS

In our opinion the difference in the frequency of the use of the words “family” in “The man of property” (109 times) and “семья” in “War and peace” (15 times) is related to the peculiarities of the novel, the first one being devoted to the family of the Forsytes, the second one – to the war between Russia and France and its impact to the life of the upper class families.

Galsworthy portrays “family” as a formidable unit of society, or society “in miniature” with its stable traditions, where the older generation tries to control that the family remains faithful to them. On this stage of our research we can assume that the conclusion about the traditions in the British family can be referred to the cultural level. The family reveals a number of positive and negative characteristics, some of them remaining debatable.

In Tolstoy’s work there is no image of one particular family; several families introduced in the work are given various characterizations, some having more positive features than others. Alongside with the negative characteristics of the family the emphasis is made on warm and sincere relationships observed between members of some families, which can be referred to cultural peculiarities of Russian families.

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